

Qualitative Study on Management of Nigerian Education System using Community Participation Models at Secondary School Level of Education

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Abstract

This paper focuses on qualitative study on management of Nigerian education system using community participation models at secondary school level of education. Based on the critical role these models play in understanding the different phenomenon in community participation practice in education, this paper aims to deconstruct the models in the context of Nigerian secondary school education system. The significance of this exegesis is to contribute to better understanding of the different models in shaping the policy, and practice of community participation in educational management at secondary school level of education in Nigeria. In addition, a brief review of the literature shows a lack of focus in that direction thus, serving as a contribution to the body of knowledge in that regard. Literature survey design was employed to compose the paper. Bhusham, S. Model that posits on community participation strategies like Adopting community resources for enhancing quality instruction through child centred approaches, was explored among others in the paper. The paper concludes that community participation goes a long way in better management of secondary schools in Nigeria. The paper recommends, among others that, rigorous campaign have to be mounted to reorient Nigerian people on the significance and importance of community participation in the management of secondary schools in Nigeria.

Keywords: community participation, models, education system, management & Secondary Schools

Introduction

Education serves as the cornerstone of societal development, playing a pivotal role in shaping individuals and preparing them for active participation in the community, (Fagerlind and Saha 2016). Education is multifaceted in nature and transcends the mere transmission of knowledge; it encompasses the cultivation of skills, values, and critical thinking abilities, contributing to the holistic development of individuals and society. In the new world order impacted by internet and digital technologies, education prepares individuals for life and provides them the skills to navigate the complexities of the inter-relations between man and his environment. Education provides the tools for critical thinking and problem solving (Abbas, Aman, Nurunnabi, & Bano (2019). Considering the role of education in shaping the growth and development of society, (Depaepe, 2012), the effective management of education is imperative.

Against this backdrop, educational institutions from lower level schools (particularly at secondary school level) to tertiary or universities require a strong and focused leadership to forge a school climate within the components that constitute an effective and efficient learning environment. Education management is the coordination of policies, curriculum development, human resources, finances, and community engagement to create a conducive space for both educators and learners, (Medina, Cosby, & Grim 2020). An important component of education management is community participation, since education is a collective endeavor, fostering community involvement is an integral and critical component of the educational system. Community participation in education management is the active engagement of parents, local community or residents within and around the school and various stakeholders in decision-making, planning, and support for educational venture, (Kusumaningrum, Ulfatin, Maisyaroh, Triwiyanto, & Gunawan, 2017). This collaborative approach underscores the interdependence between educational institutions (like secondary schools) and the communities they serve, thus, reinforcing shared responsibility for the success of the educational enterprise. The interconnection and relationship between education, education management and

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community participation is very essential for the creation of a dynamic, inclusive and responsive learning environment (Kusumaningrum et al., 2017). Understanding these relationships can enhance the quality of education, promote students success and contribute to the development of the broader society. A comprehensive exegesis of the models that explains different strategies and approaches to facilitate effective community participation at secondary school level of education management is therefore significant.

The Merriam-Webster Dictionary (2024) defined Model as usually miniature representation of something; a pattern of something to be made; a type or design of product; an example for imitation or emulation and a set of plans for a building. In education management, model refers to a structured and systematic representation or framework that describes, guides, and prescribes the processes, interactions and elements involved in managing educational institutions, (Bush, 2006; 2020; Ghasemy, & Hussin, 2014). Model in the context of this paper refers to a means of explanation and or imitation for good way of managing education system. Over the years, some models of community participation in education management have emerged in different communities and have gained popularity and significance in the community practice field (Mukhtar, 2021). These models include Goodland, J. Model, Bhusham S. Model and Ubuntu Theory of Management. Because of their popularity and significance, these models appear to be some of the most prominent in community participation discourse and practice.

Based on the critical role these models play in understanding the different phenomenon in community participation practice in education, this paper aims to deconstruct the models in the context of Nigerian education system at secondary school level. The significance of this exegesis is to contribute to better understanding of the different models in shaping the policy, and practice of community participation in educational management at secondary school level of education in Nigeria. In addition, a brief review of the literature shows a lack of focus in that direction thus, serving as a contribution to the body of knowledge in that regard. Consequently, the details in the paper will serve as an adroit cudgel for educationist, educators, education managers and relevant stakeholders in the Nigerian education ecosystem. The rest of the paper is structured in the following order: presentation of the different models in focus, discussions on the models, contextual relevance and its implications as well as the summary and conclusion and recommendations.

Goodland J. Model

Goodland (1984:35-39) in Rolfe (2015) in his massive study “A Place Called School” schooling over 300 years history, Goodland and his colleagues identified four broad goals of the school management

- Academic, including a broad array of knowledge and intellectual skills.
- Vocational aimed at readiness for the world of work and economic responsibilities.
- Social, Civic, including skills and behaviour for participating in complex democratic society.
- Personal, including the development of individual talent and self-expression

Source (Sadker and Sdker, 1991)

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**Figure 3: Goodland Goals of School Management
Implications of Goodland J. Model in the management of Nigerian education system using community participation models at secondary school level of education**

In this model (Goodland J. Model) social, civic, including skills and behaviour for participating in complex democratic society have been highlighted as one of the goals of school. This goal can never be met without the participation of the community. This is because the social, civic values and behaviour for participating in complex democratic society are determined by particularly the culture and or orientation of the community. The community therefore is in the best position to be involved in meeting that goal of social, civic, including skills and behaviour for participating in complex democratic society and that makes the community a key stakeholder in the management of Nigerian secondary school and as well the education system.

Therefore, in managing secondary school education system in Nigeria, particularly in designing and executing educational curriculum, culture and orientation of communities have to be religiously considered. This will go a long way in building confidence in the communities members in the viability and validity of the education system, it will also create and project a sense of ownership of the education system in the communities. This will as well play a good role in avoiding resistance from the communities as it happened when Western Education was introduced in Nigeria and particularly in Northern Nigeria. Northern Nigerian people resisted Western and or colonial education when the British colonialist introduced it. They did not begin to accept it until when subjects like Islamic Studies and local Malams/Anakallahu (local Islamic teachers and scholars) were involved in the teaching-learning operations in the education system.

Another point that supports the assertion is the debate around introduction of Sex Education, into the Nigerian Secondary schools curriculum. When it was introduced into the curriculum without adequate consultation and community involvement, it was vehemently rejected. This was because Sex Education sounded alien to the culture and orientation of some of Nigerian communities. Another case in point is the case of Adolescent Girl-child Initiative for Learning and Empowerment (AGILE) in 2023 in Kano and Katsina States. AGILE is a project of the World Bank that is focused on the promotion of girl-child education. The project faced resistance from particularly Islamic scholars in Kano State and it was rejected by Emir of Katsina. In Kano, there had to be a review of the AGILE document to address the cultural and orientational concerns of the community by the teaming-up of the project officials and some Islamic scholars in the State before it was accepted. Therefore, community culture and orientation have to be handled with care as they are organic in achieving the goals of school and by extension the education system goals.

Bhusham, S. Model

Bhusham (2000:77) in Chima and Itabita (2018), stated that interaction and networking for mutual benefit partnership have become an integral part of any educational programme. This trend considerably reflected the school and community and their purposeful interaction as a focal for changes in school education. In Bushman's own words, "A meaningful partnership between school and community would enhance individual student education, promote parent organizations, participation in school's daily operations. It is basically a change initiative".

Realising the importance of school community partnership for quality education, the following strategies may be considered for optimal efficiency

1. Developing school-based management and community participation in the affairs of the school by forming a coalition between communities and government.
2. Transferring some degree of ownership of school to the local communities by empowering them to demand quality education.
3. Adopting community resources for enhancing quality instruction through child centred approaches.
4. Development of school staff as a team that establishes links and respect with the community.
5. Promotion of mutual trust and faith while taking collaborative decisions

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Source: Bhushan (2000)

Figure 8 Conceptual Model of School Community Participation

Implications of Bhushan, S. Model in the management of Nigerian education system using community participation models at secondary school level of education

Therefore, this model also supports the advantage of community participation in the management of secondary schools in Nigeria. This is clear and categorical where the model mentions developing school-based management and community participation in the affairs of the school by forming a coalition between communities and government. The coalition can be made in form of forum where the communities and the government meet together to deliver on issues that matter in progress and development of secondary school. This supports the idea of School-Based Management Committee (SBMC) in our Nigerian secondary school.

Ubuntu Theory of Management

The evolution of Ubuntu Theory of Management (UTM) can be dated to the early 1930s by Mugumbate and Nyanguru; Tran and Wall when the saying was determined from the adage ‘I am because we are.’ This saying was raised from communal engagements and commitment toward shared community goals through love, selflessness, and communalism (Mugumbate and Nyanguru, 2013 in Onaolapo and Makhasane, 2023). The development of Ubuntu was slow because of the infiltration of Western paradigms that came with education in Africa (Swartz and Davies, 1997 in Onaolapo and Makhasane, 2023). This was evident in the Western scholarship and literature that generally relegated the values of Ubuntu espouses to the back in the league of other management theories.

These Westernized theories, however, failed to address learner indiscipline in the African context because the expected goal of the theories was defeated because of the lacuna set between objectives and achieved objectives (Inyang, 2008 in Onaolapo and Makhasane, 2023). In the struggle to find an indigenous effective solution to an African educational management setting, Ubuntu gradually became a suitable approach to a more humane approach to scientific management theory and has become a strong force to reckon with over the years (Ngubane and Makua, 2021 in Onaolapo and Makhasane, 2023). The indiscipline in schools today points to the fact that leadership theories that emanated from the Western context and ideologies have provided limited means to manage the problem in the African context (Msila, 2008 and Ncube, 2010 in Onaolapo and Makhasane, 2023).

Implications of Ubuntu Theory of Management in the management of Nigerian education system using community participation models at secondary school level of education

Africans are known to have a lifestyle of living in kinships and based in communal life in form of villages, town ships and extended families. This makes them to have an idea of coming together to identify their problems and work together to solve them. This is because they learn that a damage to one is a damage to all and thus the emergence of the adage “I am because we are” as explained by UTM. The adage means an individual cannot live in isolation, he has to come together with the others to have a better and fulfilled life. Therefore, in managing issues in secondary schools in Nigeria UTM buttresses the effectiveness of community participation. This is clearly indicated at the instance when Western school management theories failed to address

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issues in schools like indiscipline as explained by the UTM. This testifies to the fact that indigenous problems are effectively solved by indigenous solutions. Therefore, community would be the answer in better management of secondary school in Nigeria.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the exploration of various models of community participation in education management has provided valuable insights into the diverse approaches and strategies employed to foster collaboration between educational institutions like secondary schools and their surrounding communities. The examination of models such as Goodland, Busham and Ubuntu Theory of Management has revealed a rich tapestry of theoretical frameworks, each offering unique perspectives on the dynamics of community involvement. A common feature among these models is the recognition of community participation as an important component in the effective governance and enhancement of educational outcomes. Whether through Goodland's emphasis on social, civic, including skills and behaviour for participating in complex democratic society or Bhusham's that stated that interaction and networking for mutual benefit partnership have become an integral part of any educational programme or UTM that encourages communal engagements and commitment toward shared community goal; the models collectively underscore the significance of engaging stakeholders beyond the school walls.

However, differences also exist among the models, reflecting the complexity of community participation in diverse educational contexts. The nuanced differences in emphasis, implementation strategies, and stakeholder roles presented by the various models highlight the need for tailored approaches that align with the specific needs and dynamics of individual communities. As educational leaders and policymakers consider the implications of these models in the Nigerian context, it becomes evident that a one-size-fits-all approach is inadequate in the management of secondary school education. Therefore, the nuanced understanding gained from examining the models of community participation encourages a more comprehensive and context-specific approach to community participation in education management particularly in Nigerian secondary schools.

The synthesis of these models not only contributes to our theoretical understanding of community participation but also provides practical insights for educators, administrators, and policymakers particularly in Nigeria. The multifaceted nature of these models challenges us to adopt adaptive and responsive strategies that consider the unique socio-cultural, economic, and demographic characteristics of each community. In moving forward, it is imperative that future research and practice continue to build on these insights, acknowledging the evolving nature of educational landscapes and the dynamic relationships between schools and communities. By embracing the diversity of models presented in this paper, we can foster a more inclusive, collaborative, and effective approach to community participation in secondary school education management in Nigeria.

Recommendations

From the foregone, the paper recommends as follows:

1. People in Nigerian communities should be made to understand that education is enormous and government cannot single-handedly provide it without the help from the other quarters in the communities. To provide education particularly at secondary school level there is need for good management that communities have to be involved to do it effectively and efficiently
2. Rigorous campaign have to be mounted to reorient Nigerian people on the significance and importance of community participation in managing secondary schools
3. Government should consider communities as key stakeholders in the formulation and execution of education policies particularly at secondary school level and relate with them as such. This will go a long way in boosting the morale of the communities members and promoting sense of ownership and belonging in managing the secondary schools
4. Community participation fora in managing secondary schools like SMBC should be established where there is none in all the secondary schools in Nigeria and be reinvigorated where there is
5. Government and communities should come together and brainstorm to come up with more alternatives and innovations in community participation for better secondary schools management.

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